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Logorhythmics in the System of Corrective Work for Young Preschool Children with Cerebral Palsy (Cp)

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***Abstract:** This article provides recommendations for speech therapy rhythmic sessions with young preschool children who have cerebral palsy. It also discusses the specific characteristics of speech in this category of children and offers guidance for conducting logopedic rhythmic exercises with them.*

***Key words:** Cerebral palsy in children, speech, skills, phonetic-phonemic disorders, correction, logorhythmic tools.*

INTRODUCTION

Logopedic rhythmic, a universal tool for developing children's motor skills, combines movement exercises with the pronunciation of speech material and music.

Authors provide several definitions of logorhythmics. M.Yu. Kartushina defines logorhythmics as a system of musical and movement exercises used for corrective speech therapy needs. She emphasizes that although logorhythmics has an organized structure, it is only a supplementary component of the speech therapy training system, as logorhythmic exercises are always subordinate to the goals of speech therapy. N.A. Lukina and I.F. Saricheva consider logorhythmics "a new method of speech correction that combines musical rhythm with the use of words." O.A. Novikovskaya describes logorhythmic therapy as a "comprehensive methodology that incorporates speech therapy, musical-rhythmic, and physical education techniques."

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

G.A. Volkova defines logorhythmics from three perspectives: as a specific form of active therapy, as a means of influence within a complex of methods, and as an academic subject.

The initial concept of logopedic rhythm is based on the harmony of speech, music, and movement. The interrelationships among these components can vary. This is determined by the predominance of one element or the connections between them.

The second concept of speech therapy rhythm necessitates its integration into any rehabilitation methods for educating, training, and treating individuals with various developmental disorders and speech impairments.

In her research, G.A. Volkova distinguishes the tasks of speech therapy rhythmic and emphasizes that as a result of performing health-improving functions, children with speech impairments experience strengthening of their musculoskeletal system, development of respiratory, motor, and sensory functions, and formation of a sense of balance, proper posture, gait, and graceful movements.

According to the same author, the implementation of educational tasks contributes to the formation of motor skills and abilities, the development of spatial awareness, and the ability to move freely in space in relation to other people and objects. Moreover, this process serves to enhance agility, strength, endurance, adaptability, coordination of movements, and organizational skills.

G.A. Volkova emphasized, addressing educational tasks develops a sense of rhythm and enhances the ability to perceive rhythmic expressiveness in music, movements, and speech. Moreover, it improves the capacity to comprehend musical images and refines the skills of performing rhythmic and expressive movements in accordance with these images. In other words, it facilitates the ability to take on different personas, demonstrate artistic and creative abilities, cultivate positive personal qualities, foster a sense of community, master rules in various types of activities, and develop other skills.

The corrective direction of the exercises is determined by taking into account the mechanism and structure of speech disorders.

The application of speech therapy rhythmic tools in working with young preschool-aged children with speech and language disorders addresses the following issues: activating higher mental functions through developing all types of attention (visual, auditory); expanding memory capacity; enhancing visual and auditory perception; developing tactile-kinesthetic and musculoskeletal sensations in the child's body; assisting in the formation of motor skills in the child, such as walking, jumping, turning, throwing and catching a ball, performing movements independently and collectively, as well as introducing the child to elements of dance movements; developing a sense of musical rhythm and auditory-motor coordination.

Principles of applying logopedic rhythmic:

1. The intrinsic connection between movement and music (due to music's powerful emotional impact and rich expressive means, there exists the possibility to infinitely diversify the characteristics of movement techniques and exercises).
2. Incorporation of speech materials into logorhythmic tools (words can be used in various forms: song lyrics, round dances, dramatic performances with singing, staged scenes on a specified theme, instructions given by the leader in active games).

RESULT

Experts (Volkova G. A., Kuznetsova Ye. A., Novikovskaya O. A.) recommend the use of the following methods in speech therapy rhythmic:

1. Attention activating exercises. Exercises in this section help stimulate children's attention, develop voluntary attention, and enhance the ability to respond quickly and accurately to visual and auditory stimuli. "These exercises strengthen visual, auditory, and motor memory; develop delayed recall abilities; expand auditory-verbal memory capacity; and contribute to the reinforcement of auditory-speech traces, the ability to concentrate, and various other aspects of the child's volitional sphere."
2. Introductory exercises for practicing basic types of movements; orientation in space; coordination of movements and control of muscle tone.

This includes exercises for marching and running in various directions, as well as activities to reinforce basic types of movement. These exercises help to develop initial skills in walking individually and in pairs around a circle, maintaining proper spacing when moving in one direction along a circular path, lining up in formation, arranging in single file and in pairs, light jogging, and jumping with both feet together.

According to E. Kuznetsova, all these tasks teach children to orient themselves in space and reinforce basic concepts such as: left, right, forward, backward, sideways, side-by-side, circular, in front, behind, above the head, under the feet, consecutive, and others. Additionally, it teaches children to perform turns, change the direction of movement at the command "Turn!," and move towards and away from the center. When performing exercises that regulate muscle tone, children learn to alternately tense and relax their muscles (as demonstrated in games using roly-poly dolls and Petrushka puppets).

3. Exercises that develop a sense of musical rhythm.

Novikovskaya O.A. emphasizes that when performing these exercises, it is important to pay attention to the emotional content and structure of the music. It is necessary to cultivate in children the skill of reflecting elements of musical expressiveness in their movements, particularly phrases, tempo, and dynamics. For this purpose, alternating dance movements such as "kabluchok" - "spring," clapping - "spring," as well as throwing and passing a ball around the circle can be used. Thus, this approach allows for diversifying the nature of movements while maintaining the ability to perceive the heard music as a complete and finished whole.

4. Exercises that develop listening and speech comprehension abilities. Breathing exercises. Singing.

Volkova G.A. draws our attention to the inclusion of exercises in this section aimed at developing children's auditory and speech-auditory perception. These exercises are designed to help children distinguish between household noises, sounds made by animals and objects, and the sounds of musical instruments. Specifically, they develop the ability to differentiate the sounds of musical instruments such as rattles, tambourines, flutes, whistles, bells, and spoons. Such exercises foster children's skills in comparing and distinguishing sound-producing objects based on their timbre, volume, and pitch. Additionally, these activities enhance children's ability to compare and identify simple rhythms presented to them.

Exercises that develop the prosodic structure of speech and voice are of great importance. The aim of such exercises is for the child to correctly pronounce the stressed syllable in a chain of syllables after the speech therapist, and then in words with increasingly complex syllable structures. This also includes identifying one of two words according to the rhythmic pattern proposed by the speech therapist. Kuznetsova E.V. emphasizes that to increase children's interest in such tasks, using the method of passing a medium-sized ball to each other yields good results. This method directs the child's attention to listening attentively to adults and correctly repeating the suggested speech pattern.

To reinforce the intonations of questions, requests, affirmations, exclamations, and admonitions, exercises are performed based on simple syllables. According to E.V. Kuznetsova, if familiar examples from life are given, such as asking to buy a toy, expressing joy about going for a walk, or prohibiting walking in a puddle, children will easily complete such tasks.

According to Novikovskaya O.A., this section includes exercises that develop speech and singing breath control. It is crucial to cultivate in children the ability to exhale for prolonged periods at a steady rate, as well as to develop their skill in creating a strong airflow through the mouth. In developing singing breath control, it is sufficient to teach children diaphragmatic "abdominal" breathing, to breathe evenly and smoothly while singing, and to gently replenish air when they run short of breath during performance.

5. Speech enhancement exercises.

These exercises are conducted both with musical accompaniment and without music. "The main task," emphasizes E.V. Kuznetsova, "is to rhythmically perform the poetic text in harmony with movements. The distinctive feature of this work is that it employs the simplest rhythmic forms with counts of two, three, or four, and uses durations such as eighth notes, quarter notes, and half notes in 2/4 or 4/4 time signatures."

CONSIDERATION

Speech exercises without music for working with stuttering children were first proposed by V.A. Griner. G.A. Volkova presents the following requirements for conducting such exercises:

- movements should not be artificial;
- poetic material should have the following characteristics:
 - a) various corrective approaches: for normalizing tempo and rhythm, expanding vocabulary, and automating sound pronunciation;
 - b) specific dynamic measure that allows synchronizing hand, foot, and body movements with speech rhythm;
 - c) medium-length lines, as it is difficult to match movements to long lines;
 - d) should be enriched with verbs for describing actions;
 - e) should have a plot line or character to avoid mechanical movements and establish a logical connection between the text and actions;
 - f) additionally, poems should be selected considering the age, speech, and motor abilities of the participants.

6. Playing musical instruments.

The use of musical instruments is also incorporated into logorhythmic sessions for children. As Novikovskaya O.A. emphasizes, this activity holds particular importance because it introduces children to the world of music and helps develop their creative abilities. Some musical toys serve as visual didactic tools. They not only foster children's musical perception skills but also fulfill the function of familiarizing them with the fundamental elements of musical literacy.

7. Active games.

According to Kuznetsova Ye.V., this section includes games that develop speed, strength, agility, and endurance. These games foster children's ability to work in a team, cultivate a competitive spirit, strengthen their emotional and volitional qualities, and also enhance figurative thinking and creative imagination.

8. Dance and pantomime

According to G.A. Volkova, dance and pantomime are the most suitable types of artistic activity for shaping and developing children's creativity. One of the most important conditions for developing creativity in dance among preschool-aged children is their conscious attitude towards the means of dance expression and mastery of the language of pantomimic and dance movements. However, as E.M. Kuznetsova emphasizes, preschool-aged children cannot independently achieve understanding and mastery of this movement language. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them this language.

CONCLUSION

Thus, during logorhythmic exercises, the child's motor skills normalize, and speech disorders are eliminated naturally, without the child even being aware of it.

To successfully develop grammatical knowledge and skills in children with cerebral palsy, a comprehensive approach to their mental and speech development is essential.

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